

Exploring a BPMS system for learning production management with simulation of manufacturing scenarios

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Abstract

The approach by processes, and business processes management (BPM) in particular, has been increasingly studied by academia and more adopted in the business environment, due to its capabilities. Therefore, educational establishments should consider teaching and learning of technologies (such as BPMS systems) that systematize and facilitate the analysis, design and (re)engineering of organizations. Simulation systems can be used to develop active learning and improve student engagement in engineering classes. This work aims to explore the use of BPM in such a way that it might integrate with pedagogical practices. Specifically, we carry out a preliminary evaluation of a BPMS system in the simulation of manufacturing processes, aimed at the future teaching and learning of undergraduate students on Production Engineering courses, for the assimilation of knowledge about Production Management through life-like examples. The context under consideration was the manufacture of products assuming different physical layouts, which represent the positioning of the transforming resources of a hypothetical production environment, determining how raw material and transformed resources will flow through operational procedures. Using a version of the Bizagi software modeling and simulation, we identify the facility with which the processes are modeled, as well as quick data entry and simulation of these processes, could be modeled with the software analyzed. However, some difficulties in modeling and simulation with Bizagi were discovered with regards to the consideration of manufacturing processes by batch. That is, in this initial investigation of the simulation functionalities of the system, it was not possible to use batches of different sizes. This difficulty limits the use of the BPMS for simulating manufacturing scenario concepts and, consequently, the use of the system for pedagogical activities in production management classes.

Keywords: Process Management; Simulation; Production Management; Active learning.

1 Introduction

There is a worldwide trend for market unification and the globalization of the economy. Because of this, there is a need for companies to find new ways to improve their processes, using, for example, BPM (Business Process Management), whose approach is management of a company by processes. To support modeling, simulation, execution and process management activities, appropriate languages and BPMS (Business Process Management System) tools are required (Cheung & Hidders, 2011; Association of Business Process Management Professionals, 2013; Brocke & Mendling, 2018; Dumas et al., 2018).

Modeling and simulation techniques have been used to better describe the business processes of organizations, and are the basis for the application of other typical techniques of design, operation and company management (Kučař & Vondrák, 2016; Bisogno et al., 2016; Vukšić et al. 2017).

In classrooms where the course is centered on the instructor, many students lack motivation. They adopt a passive position in front of the teacher and find content, which in most cases does not correspond to initial expectations, fragmented. As a result, they are unable to think analytically.

Modeling techniques and simulation systems have already been used successfully for teaching and learning in various contexts, but there is a lack of work in the area of BPM and Manufacturing Processes. Before using a modeling system pedagogically, it is necessary to create possible models considering scenarios and testing the features of the simulation system to be used.

This work aims to explore the use of Process Based Management in an integrated way. In particular, it aims to carry out a preliminary evaluation of a BPMS module in the simulation of processes aimed at the future creation of possible pedagogical practices for the teaching/learning of undergraduate students on Production (or

Industrial) Engineering courses, using the assimilation of the Production Management content through life-like manufacturing scenarios. More specifically, the functionality of BPMS was tested and analyzed in two different production configurations, associated with two typical layouts from the theory of production management: the functional arrangement (or process layout) and the arrangement by product (or product layout).

The process-based approach and BPM has been increasingly studied by the academic environment and has been increasingly adopted in the business environment, due to its capabilities. Therefore, educational establishments must teach and make use of technologies (such as BPMS systems) that systematize and facilitate the analysis, design and (re)engineering of organizations.

Thus, after presenting the theoretical basis on the subject, this article will present the research method and the development of the work, followed by the results achieved and an evaluation of the use of a BPMS system to simulate production planning concepts.

2 Theoretical Basis

2.1 Business Processes Management

Managing business processes efficiently is critical to the success of an organization. However, such management is more complicated than it may seem, as business processes interact with each other. And yet, the more processes are managed, the greater the potential for them to bring benefits and results for a company (Tarhan, Turetken & Reijers, 2016; Brocke & Mendling, 2018; Dumas et al., 2018).

According to Minoli (2008), the objectives of BPM are to understand the different business processes of a company; restructure the processes in order to optimize their operation based on the knowledge of processes; and assist in decision making, thereby supporting the interoperability of business processes.

BPM practices lead to an organization centered on processes, reducing its dependence on functional and territorial structures. The benefits offered by BPM are: continuous improvement and innovation, visibility, compliance (acting in accordance with the rules), standardization, greater agility, teamwork and cost reduction (White & Miers, 2008). Among several BPM cycles proposed in the literature, Baldam, Valle and Rozenfeld (2014) created a Unified BPM Life Cycle for process management, which is composed of four phases (Figure 1). The mapping, modeling and simulation of processes are carried out mainly in the Process Modeling and Optimization phase.

2.2 Mapping and Modeling of Business Processes

The objective of process mapping is to identify and understand all activities in an organization, thereby establishing its design as it is; and from that information, to improve or modify it, in order to arrive at the way you want it to be (Assunção, 2018). Some basic options for gathering information for analytical processes, being considered good practice for the management of business processes, are: observation; interviews; simulation; and do rather than observe (Association of Business Process Management Professionals, 2013). However, there are more appropriate methods for mapping processes, such as SIPOC (Suppliers, Inputs, Process, Outputs, and Customer). It is a simple language graphic that defines the process map, the purpose of which is to identify processes and management so that everyone involved understands their responsibilities.

The mapping activity in the literature overlaps, or is confused with, the modeling activity for some authors and research context, since documenting the information gathering of mapped processes is necessary, that is, process models end up being the results of the mapping. Simply put, Mertins and Jochem (2005) define models as reference guides for support and documentation throughout a project, improvement or reengineering of a company.

Figure 1. Life cycle for the BPM (adapted from Baldam, Valle and Rozenfeld (2014)).

Business process modeling is a way of organizing work and resources - whether people, equipment or information - in order to achieve an organization's objectives. Furthermore, it clarifies how the work is performed, representing the integration structure of an organization's units, providing structured information on the use of resources, the execution of tasks and the delivery of finished products to customers, without necessarily having a relationship with information technology systems (Minoli, 2008; Association of Business Process Management Professionals, 2013).

There are several notations and languages for process modeling, such as the extensions to UML (Unified Modeling Language), EPC (Event-driven Process Chain), and BPMN (Business Process Management Notation) (Association of Business Process Management Professionals, 2013).

BPMN refers to a series of standard icons for the design of processes, which facilitate a user's understanding by providing a set of builders that allow the creation of Business Process Diagrams, built through a basic set of builders (White & Miers, 2008). These symbols or icons are divided into five basic categories: Flow Objects, Data, Connecting Objects, Swimlanes, and Artifacts (Object Management Group, 2014).

2.3 BPMS Tools for Process Modeling and Simulation

In order to support the activities of mapping, modeling, simulation, execution and management of processes, not only are adequate methods and languages necessary, but also computational tools that automate these activities, such as BPMS (Business Process Management System) (Cheung & Hidders, 2011 ; Association of Business Process Management Professionals, 2013; Sebastian et al., 2014; Medoh & Telukdarie, 2017; Pereira & Freitas, 2019).

BPMS systems automate the BPM methodology enabling processes to be modeled, modified and improved with speed and control. Existing BPMS tools should be evaluated according to their characteristics and functionality, aiming to use the one that best adapts to an organization's conditions of use (Association of Business Process Management Professionals, 2013; Baldam, Valle and Rozenfeld, 2014).

There is a range of specific tools to support mapping, model generation, simulation and business process analysis, known as BPA (Business Process Analysis) tools. BPMS (Business Processes Management Systems) tools, in addition to offering support for process modeling and simulation, have functionalities aimed at the execution and management of processes. The analysis capacity of these latter tools is generally less in relation

to the BPA tools, and some studies compare and research their integration (Blechar, 2008; Norton et al., 2010; Cheung & Hidders, 2011; Sebastian et al., 2014; Medoh & Telukdarie, 2017).

3 Research Method

The research in this study is classified as exploratory and qualitative in order to carry out a preliminary evaluation of the characteristics of a BPMS module, with the aim of using it in production management pedagogical scenarios. In this initial study, we chose to start with a simpler production system context and model. The steps were: (i) Definition of the simulation context and production layouts; (ii) Definition of the BPMS software for process simulation; (iii) Modeling the manufacturing scenarios and process (iv) Inputting data, such as product arrival time intervals, process activity times and machine data capacity (in this first test, we used the deterministic approach); (v) Execution of the simulation comparing and analyzing the output data; (vi) Evaluation of the BPMS as a possible tool to support teaching and learning of production management using the scenarios.

The simulation being considered relates to the manufacture of gears. However, in order not to dwell on technical issues in this article, this study considers a generic scenario with the production of 3 products (P1, P2 e P3), assuming different physical arrangements. Physical arrangements represent the positioning of transforming resources in an environment, determining how the raw material, transformed resources, information and customers will flow through operations. There are four main types of physical arrangements: positional, functional, cellular, and by product. This study simulates two different production configurations, associated with two different arrangements: functional (or process) layout and product layout. In the functional physical arrangement, each product flows differently within the environment, so that each one will perform a sequence necessary for their production, and the sequence may be different from the flow of the next product. With the product layout the physical arrangement is per product and the raw material follows a pre-established schedule showing which resources it will flow through.

4 Development and Results

In the simulated production scenario, the raw materials needed to manufacture the products arrive at the initial stock through an external supplier. The products P1, P2 and P3 go through 5 machines (A, B, C, D and E) for manufacturing activities. For the processes simulation, the manufacture of 300 batches of products is defined, with the arrival of instances at an interval of 300 minutes. The simulation time is defined as being 30 days, sufficient for the production of all batches. The product queue is managed through a concept known as FIFO (First In First Out).

In production processes, the capacities of productive resources such as product processing times (or lead-time) are the same for the two layouts developed, in order to be able to create comparisons between the results obtained at the end of each process, and analyze the effects of the different layouts on the production process. Then, in this work, the main difference is the ways of sharing machines, since characteristics such as transport time and of set up were not considered, due to the need for simplification in this preliminary simulation presented here. Processing times are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Fictitious lead time of products for each machine

Lead time for each machine (hours)			
Machines/Products	P1	P2	P3
Machine A	2	3	2,5
Machine B	4	2	2
Machine C	3	4	2
Machine D	3	2	5
Machine E	2	2,5	1

For the experiment, the Bizagi modeling and simulation module (Version 3.1) was used due to its ease of modeling (it supports BPMN notation) and the integrated way it can be used with the simulation, without the need for reworking with interfaces or the reintroduction of input information from the process model.

Using the software, the process model was built according to the scenarios described (illustrated by Figure 2) and then the parameters of time and types and number of machines for the simulation were inserted. In both layouts, the number of machines (types A, B, C, D e E) was defined as three of each type (Figure 3). To make an initial simplified analogy to physical arrangements, the two types of production layouts were associated with different machine distribution modes: machines dedicated to a specific product, in the case of the production line with product layout (Figure 2); and machines shared by all products in the case of the functional layout.

Figure 2. Manufacturing process model with product layout developed in Bizagi.

Figure 3. Data entry illustration related to resources in Bizagi.

Some of the difficulties in modeling and simulation are related to the consideration of manufacturing processes by batch; when exploring the use of the simulation functionalities of the system it was not possible to use

batches of different sizes, such as, for example, a heat treatment process of gears, which in reality generally uses batch processing.

Also, due to these difficulties, the instance of input from the simulation was considered to be a whole batch of product (P1 or P2 or P3), and different times were defined for each product on each machine for these batch sizes. At first the simulation was programmed so that the proportion of products P1, P2 and P3 to be manufactured were equal to one third, with the final distribution being affected by the logic of the distribution of the software.

The results were analyzed both through graphical presentation and through reports (Figures 2 and 4). With these hypothetical scenarios, far from wanting to portray all the reality in this simply model, some effects can be perceived that help demonstrate a number of the concepts. For example, issues such as the best or worst load distribution among the machines and a shorter or longer time for the completion of the production of one or other type of layout can be identified.

Name	Type	Instances completed	Instances started	Min. time	Max. time	Avg. time	Total time	Min. time waiting resource	Max. time waiting resource
Process- Product Layout	Process	300	300	12h 30m	9d 4h 30m	3d 10h 8m 54s	1026d 20h 30m		
NoneStart	Start event	300							
Activity P1 Machine A	Task	103	103	2h	9h	3h 29m 42s	15d	0	7h
Activity P1 Machine B	Task	103	103	4h	5d	2d 21h 33m 47s	298d 13h	0	4d 20h
Activity P1 Machine C	Task	103	103	3h	3h	3h	12d 21h	0	0
Activity P1 Machine D	Task	103	103	3h	3h	3h	12d 21h	0	0
Activity P1 Machine E	Task	103	103	2h	2h	2h	8d 14h	0	0
NoneEnd	End event	300							
ExclusiveGateway	Gateway	300	300						
Activity P2 Machine A	Task	96	96	3h	17h	8h 26m 52s	33d 19h	0	14h

Figure 4. Example of a simulation report in Bizagi.

5 Conclusions

Modeling, simulation and business process management (BPM) techniques are important tools for the design and management of production systems, and the teaching/learning in conjunction with typical production management scenarios can provide greater motivation for students and a better understanding of the subjects covered, when compared to classes based purely on theoretical models and not associated with real situations or life-like situations. This study carried out a preliminary evaluation of a BPMS module with the simulation of processes aimed at the future teaching/learning of undergraduate students of Production Engineering courses for the assimilation of the BPM and Production Management content through life-like examples. Specifically, two different production configurations were simulated and analyzed, associated with two different layouts: functional and product arrangement.

It was discovered that using a version of the Bizagi module for the modeling and simulation of different production layouts clearly facilitated the modeling processes, as well as demonstrating greater agility for the data entry simulation of these processes. However, in this first exploratory research of the simulation functionalities in the system, there were some difficulties, such as the consideration of batch manufacturing processes (mainly the use of batches of varying sizes), which limit the use of this simulation module for teaching/learning of Production Management concepts involving different physical arrangements of machines.

Part of the difficulties may be due to the authors' inexperience with the system. Therefore, further investigation is considered necessary for conclusions on the adequacy of teaching and learning of BPM and themes related to Production Management with this or new versions of BPMS from the market to be fully understood.

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